

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL-CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK FAMILY SETTINGS

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Abstract: This thesis explores and compares the national-cultural characteristics of speech etiquette used in family settings in the English and Uzbek languages. The aim of this study is to provide a comprehensive examination of the cultural norms and values that influence communication patterns within families, shedding light on the similarities and differences between these two distinct cultural contexts. By identifying and analyzing the various components of speech etiquette, such as politeness strategies, intergenerational dynamics, and gender roles, this research intends to deepen our understanding of how language use is shaped by cultural factors and to contribute to a cross-cultural understanding of communication practices within the family unit.

Keywords: Family, communication, relations, culturally marked cross-cultural, linguistic picture of the world, speech etiquette

Introduction. The objective of this thesis is to examine the national-cultural characteristics of speech etiquette in English and Uzbek family settings. By analyzing the linguistic practices, cultural customs, and social factors associated with verbal communication within these two language communities, this study aims to deepen our understanding of the role of language and culture in shaping familial interactions.

Chapter 1: Overview of English and Uzbek Speech Etiquette

1.1 Historical Context and Language Development: Provides a brief background on the evolution and development of the English and Uzbek languages, considering the historical, social, and cultural factors that have influenced their speech etiquette.

Chapter 2: Speech Etiquette Chapter "The study aims to explore and compare the national-cultural characteristics of speech etiquette employed within family settings in English and Uzbek languages, examining the various linguistic and sociocultural factors that influence communication norms and practices. By analyzing the similarities and differences in speech patterns, politeness strategies, and familial roles, this research seeks to enhance our understanding of how language and culture intersect in shaping familial interactions in these two distinct linguistic contexts."

The family relations in Uzbek and English families are quite similar in some aspects, although differences may exist due to cultural and traditional variations.

1. Nuclear Family: Both cultures typically have nuclear families consisting of parents and their children, living together and forming the basic unit of society.

2. Extended Family: While extended families are important in Uzbek culture, they are less prevalent in English culture. Uzbek families often live together with grandparents, uncles, aunts, and cousins, fostering strong intergenerational bonds. English families commonly have closer relations with immediate family members, although extended family members may still play a significant role.

3. Gender Roles: In both cultures, traditional gender roles have been prominent, although English families now often have more equal distribution of tasks and responsibilities. In

Uzbek families, men are traditionally seen as the primary breadwinners, while women play a significant role in taking care of the household and children. However, this is gradually changing with increasing urbanization and globalization.

In both Uzbek and English families, the roles and importance of elders vary but generally hold significance. Here are some aspects related to the importance of elder roles:

1. **Wisdom and Guidance:** Elders are respected for their life experience, wisdom, and knowledge. They often serve as a source of guidance and advice for younger family members, especially when it comes to making important life decisions.
2. **Family Values and Tradition:** Elders play a crucial role in preserving and passing on family values, traditions, and cultural heritage. They ensure that important customs and rituals are upheld and contribute to the cultural identity of the family.
3. **Decision-Making:** Elders often have significant influence in family decision-making processes. Their opinions and perspectives are valued, and they may have the final say in certain matters involving family affairs, financial decisions, or major life events.
4. **Caregiving and Support:** Elders may require support and care as they age, and family members are typically responsible for ensuring their well-being.

English Language:

1. **Politeness:** English families often emphasize the use of polite language and manners during family conversations. This includes saying "please" and "thank you" when requesting or receiving something.
2. **Respect for elders:** Children are often taught to show respect to their parents and older family members by using titles such as "sir" or "ma'am" and addressing them with a polite tone.
3. **Turn-taking:** In English families, there is a clear expectation of turn-taking during conversations. Interrupting others while they are speaking is generally considered rude or impolite.
4. **Direct communication:** English families often prefer direct and clear communication. They express their thoughts and opinions openly without resorting to excessive use of non-verbal cues or implicit meanings.

Uzbek Language:

1. **Formal address:** Uzbek families often use formal address forms when speaking to their elders or people of higher status. This includes using respectful pronouns and honorifics to show deference.
2. **Respect** Comparing the national-cultural characteristics of speech etiquette used in the family in English and Uzbek languages, we can identify several differences and similarities.

In English-speaking families, politeness and indirectness are emphasized. Family members often use polite forms of address, such as "sir" or "ma'am," when speaking to parents or elders. There is a tendency to be more formal and use euphemisms when discussing sensitive topics. Parents often teach children to say "please" and "thank you" and to use expressions like "excuse me" when interrupting or leaving the table. English-speaking families also value individualism and independence, leading to more open discussions and debates within the family.

On the other hand, Uzbek-speaking families prioritize respect and collectivism. Addressing elders with proper honorifics is crucial, and children are taught to use respectful terms like

"aka" (brother) or "opa" (sister) when addressing older siblings. Uzbek families emphasize obedience and conformity.

Conclusion. Language is considered one of the most valuable and lasting achievements since the beginning of humanity. It is not an exaggeration to say that language is not only a reason for the emergence of human communication, but also a postcard that speaks about the history, mentality, value, and national cultural characteristics of different countries.

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